

CHARACTERIZATIONS OF GEOMETRIC TRIPOTENTS IN SFS-SPACES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612411>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada qirralari kuchli simmetrik fazolarda geometrik tripotentlarning geometrik tavsifi keltiriladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: qirralari kuchli simmetrik fazo, simmetrik qirra, geometrik tripotent.

Annotation. This paper presents a geometric characterization of geometric tripotents in strongly facially symmetric spaces.

Key words: strongly facially symmetric space, symmetric face, geometric tripotent.

Аннотация. В данной статье приводится геометрическая характеристика геометрических трипотентов в сильно гранево симметричных пространствах.

Ключевые слова: сильно гранево симметричные пространства, симметричная грань, геометрический трипотент.

An important problem of the theory of operator algebras is a geometric characterization of state spaces of operator algebras. In the mid-1980s, Friedman and Russo wrote the paper [1] related to this problem, in which they introduced strongly facially symmetric spaces, largely for the purpose of obtaining a geometric characterization of the predual spaces of JBW*-triples admitting an algebraic structure. Many of the properties required in these characterizations are natural assumptions for state spaces of physical systems. Such spaces are regarded as a geometric model for states of quantum mechanics.

The principal examples of complex strongly facially symmetric spaces are preduals of complex JBW*-triples, in particular, the preduals of von Neumann algebras (see [2]). In these cases, as shown in [2], geometric tripotents correspond to tripotents in a JBW*-triple and to partial isometries in a von Neumann algebra. In [3], the relationship between M-orthogonality and algebraic orthogonality in JB*-triples was studied. A purely geometric description of the algebraic concept of tripotents was obtained. This paper is devoted to the study of the relationship between M-orthogonality and orthogonality in the sense of SFS-spaces in dual space. A geometric characterization of geometric tripotents in SFS-spaces is given.

Let Z be a real or complex normed space. We say that elements $f, g \in Z$ are orthogonal and write $f \diamond g$ if $\|f + g\| = \|f - g\| = \|f\| + \|g\|$. A face F of the unit ball $Z_1 = \{f \in Z : \|f\| \leq 1\}$ is said to be norm exposed if $F = F_u = \{f \in Z_1 : u(f) = 1\}$ for some $u \in Z^*$ with $\|u\| = 1$. An element $u \in Z^*$ is called a projective unit if $\|u\| = 1$ and $u(g) = 0$ for all $g \in F_u^\diamond$ (see [1]).

A norm exposed face F_u in Z is called a symmetric face if there exists a linear isometry S_u from Z onto Z such that $S_u^2 = I$ whose fixed point set coincides with the topological direct

sum of the closure $\overline{sp} F_u$ of the linear hull of the face F_u and its orthogonal complement F_u^\diamond , i.e., with $(\overline{sp} F_u) \oplus F_u^\diamond$.

A normed space Z is strongly facially symmetric (SFS) if,

- 1) each norm exposed face in Z_1 is symmetric;
- 2) for each norm exposed face F_u of Z and each $y \in Z^*$ satisfying the conditions $\|y\|=1$ and $F_u \subset F_y$, we have $S_u y = y$, where S_u is the symmetry corresponding to F_u .

For each symmetric face F_u , contractive projections $P_k(u)$, $k=0,1,2$, on Z are defined as follows. First, $P_1(u) = (I - S_u)/2$ is the projection onto the eigenspace corresponding to the eigenvalue -1 of the symmetry S_u . Next, $P_2(u)$ and $P_0(u)$ are defined as projections of Z onto $\overline{sp} F_u$ and F_u^\diamond , respectively. The projections $P_k(u)$ are called the geometric Peirce projections. A projective unit u from Z^* is called a geometric tripotent if F_u is a symmetric face and $S_u^* u = u$ for the symmetry S_u corresponding to F_u .

Two elements a and b of a normed vector space E are said to be M-orthogonal, denoted $a \square b$, if $\|a \pm b\| = \max\{\|a\|, \|b\|\}$, (see [4]).

For a subset H of the normed vector space E , the M-orthogonal complement (briefly the M-complement) H^\square of H is defined by

$$H^\square = \{a \in E : a \square b, \forall b \in H\}.$$

For each element a of norm one the complex space E , the tangent disc S_a at a is defined by

$$S_a = \{b \in E : \|a + zb\| = 1, \forall z \in C, |z| \leq 1\}.$$

Let Z be a SFS-space. Two elements x and y of Z^* are orthogonal if one of them belongs to $P_2(u)^*(Z^*)$ and the other to $P_0(u)^*(Z^*)$ for some geometric tripotent u .

For a subset H of Z^* we let $H^\diamond = \{x \in Z^* : x \diamond y, \forall y \in H\}$ and call H^\diamond the orthogonal complement H .

Theorem 1. Let Z be a complex SFS-space and let u be an element in Z^* of norm one. Then the following conditions are equivalent:

- (i) $u \in GU$;
- (ii) $u^\square \cap Z_1^* = u^\diamond \cap Z_1^*$;
- (iii) $u^\square \cap Z_1^* = iu^\square \cap Z_1^*$;
- (iv) $S_u = u^\diamond \cap Z_1^*$

For a norm-one element u of Z_1^* , consider the sets $X_1(u)$ and $X_2(u)$ defined by

$$X_1(u) = \{y \in Z^* : \exists t > 0, \|u \pm ty\| = 1\},$$

$$X_2(u) = \{y \in Z^* : \forall z \in \square, \|u \pm zy\| = \max\{1, \|zy\|\}\}.$$

It is worth noting that the conditions $u^\square \cap Z_1^* = iu^\square \cap Z_1^*$ and $X_1(u) = X_2(u)$ are not equivalent in arbitrary complex normed vector spaces. The question is whether this equivalence

holds in reflexive complex SFS-spaces. The affirmative answer, presented in the next theorem, provides yet another metric characterization of geometric tripotents.

Theorem 2. Let Z be a complex SFS-space and let u be an element in Z^* of norm one. Then u is a geometric tripotent if and only if $X_1(u)$ and $X_2(u)$ coincide.

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